

Pathology Report Data Extraction and Processing

This repository contains a comprehensive suite of scripts designed to extract, process, analyze, and visualize structured data from pathology reports. The workflow utilizes various models and APIs, including OpenAI's GPT-4, Hugging Face's LLaMA models, and 4-bit quantized model versions provided by Ollama. Additionally, R scripts are provided for detailed statistical analysis and visualization of the extracted data.

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Requirements

Python Environment

- **Python Version:** 3.9 or higher
- **Python Packages:** Install via `pip install -r requirements.txt`
 - openai
 - huggingface_hub
 - pandas
 - numpy
 - tqdm
 - requests
 - json
 - os
 - sys
- **API Keys:**
 - **OpenAI API Key:** Required for `inference_GPT4.py`
 - **Hugging Face API Token:** Required for `inference_llama2.py` and `inference_llama3.py`

R Environment

- **R Version:** 4.0 or higher
- **R Packages:** Install using `install.packages("package_name")` or appropriate methods
 - tidyverse
 - data.table
 - ggplot2
 - dplyr
 - readr
 - stringr
 - ggpubr
 - reshape2
 - scales
 - gridExtra
 - cowplot

Ollama

Repository Structure

Script Descriptions

Python Scripts

`inference\_GPT4.py`

- **Description:** This script extracts structured data from pathology reports using the OpenAI GPT-4 API.
- **Key Features:**
 - **Input:** .xlsx file with IDs and corresponding pathology reports. (See PRAD_reports_eng.xlsx / PRAD_reports_ger.xlsx)
 - **Processing:** Sends each report to GPT-4 with a predefined zero-shot prompt.
 - **Output:** Saves extracted data/JSON files in a specified output directory and logs errors.
- **Dependencies:**
 - OpenAI API key must be added in the script under the variable 'openai_api_key'.

`inference\_llama2.py`

- **Description:** Similar to inference_GPT4.py, but utilizes the Hugging Face API to extract data using the LLaMA2 model.
- **Key Features:**
 - **Input:** .xlsx file with IDs and corresponding pathology reports. (See PRAD_reports_eng.xlsx / PRAD_reports_ger.xlsx)

- **Model Specification:** Define the LLaMA2 model variant through the 'model' variable.
- **Output:** Saves extracted data/JSON files in a specified output directory and logs errors.
- **Authentication:** Requires a valid Hugging Face API token, which has to be specified under the section 'Login huggingface'.

`inference\_llama3.py`

- **Description:** Extends the functionality of inference_llama2.py by using the LLaMA3 model for data extraction via Hugging Face API.
- **Key Features:**
 - **Input and Output:** Identical to inference_llama2.py.
 - **Model Specification:** Set to use LLaMA3 model through the model variable.
 - **Authentication:** Requires a valid Hugging Face API token, which has to be specified under the section 'Login huggingface'.

`inference\_4bit\_models.py`

- **Description:** Leverages 4-bit quantized versions of LLaMA2, LLaMA3, and Qwen2.5 models provided by Ollama for efficient data extraction.
- **Key Features:**
 - **Input:** .xlsx file with IDs and corresponding pathology reports. (See PRAD_reports_eng.xlsx / PRAD_reports_ger.xlsx)
 - **Model Selection:** Specify desired model (LLaMA2, LLaMA3, or Qwen2.5) via the 'model' variable.
 - **Efficiency:** Reduced computational overhead while maintaining performance.
 - **Output:** Saves extracted data as JSON files; includes error logging.
 - **Dependencies:** Requires Ollama setup with access to 4-bit quantized models.

`inference\_4bit\_cov.py`

- **Description:** This script uses the JSON files generated by inference_4bit_models.py to perform a chain of verification prompting approach. It controls and corrects the initial JSON outputs to improve accuracy.
- **Key Features:**
 - **Input:** JSON files generated by inference_4bit_models.py. In addition .xlsx file with IDs and corresponding pathology reports. (See PRAD_reports_eng.xlsx / PRAD_reports_ger.xlsx)
 - **Output:** Corrected JSON files after verification prompting.
 - **Dependencies:** Requires the JSON outputs from inference_4bit_models.py and related setup.

`json\_processing.py`

- **Description:** Processes JSON files generated by inference scripts to compile results, compare the data against the ground truth annotations, and prepare them for further analysis.
- **Key Features:**
 - **Input:** JSON files generated by the LLMs and a .xlsx file with ground truth data. For the format of the ground truth data table see PRAD_ground_truth.xlsx.
 - **Concatenation:** Merges individual JSON files into a comprehensive results table.
 - **Accuracy Calculation:** Compares extracted data with ground truth data of our study.
 - **Multi-Report Handling:** Prioritizes the most recent report; consults older reports if necessary.
 - **Validation:** Generates status reports indicating JSON structure integrity and preprocessing requirements.
 - **Summary:** Produces a key frequency report to identify redundant or missing keys.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Requires JSON files from the inference scripts and the ground truth data frame from our study for accuracy comparison.

R Scripts

`analysis\_16bit.R`

- **Description:** Performs comprehensive statistical analysis and visualization of data extracted by full-precision models (GPT-4, LLaMA2, LLaMA3).
- **Key Features:**
 - **Data Processing:** Reads processed results from json_processing.py and prepares datasets for analysis.
 - **Statistical Analysis:** Computes performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-scores.
 - **Visualization:** Generates figures illustrating model performance comparisons, error rates, and other relevant statistics.
 - **Reporting:** Outputs summarized statistics and plots to the results directory.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Relies on functions defined in analysis_16bit_fun.R.
 - Requires processed data files from json_processing.py.

`analysis\_4bit.R`

- **Description:** Conducts statistical analysis and visualization for data extracted by 4-bit quantized models (LLaMA2, LLaMA3, Qwen2.5).

- **Key Features:**
 - **Data Processing:** Similar to analysis_16bit.R, tailored for 4-bit model outputs.
 - **Statistical Analysis:** Evaluates and compares performance metrics across different quantized models.
 - **Visualization:** Produces figures showcasing efficiency and performance trade-offs.
 - **Reporting:** Outputs summarized statistics and plots to the results directory.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Utilizes functions from analysis_4bit_fun.R.
 - Requires processed data files from json_processing.py.

``analysis_16bit_fun.R``

- **Description:** A collection of reusable functions to support statistical analysis and plotting in analysis_16bit.R.
- **Usage:**
 - Sourced within analysis_16bit.R to provide modular and maintainable code structure.

``analysis_4bit_fun.R``

- **Description:** A collection of reusable functions to support statistical analysis and plotting in analysis_4bit.R.
- **Usage:**
 - Sourced within analysis_4bit.R for organized and efficient analysis workflows.

Usage

Python Scripts

Manually specify parameters in the script:

Running ``inference_GPT4.py``

- `<report_filename>`: Path to the input .xlsx file containing pathology reports. (See PRAD_reports_eng.xlsx / PRAD_reports_ger.xlsx)
- `<openai_api_key>`: Your OpenAI API key for authentication.
- `<output_dir>`: Directory where JSON output files will be saved.
- `<stderr_out>`: Directory where stderr output will be saved.

Running ``inference_llama2.py`` and ``inference_llama3.py``

- `<token>`: Your Hugging Face API token.
- `<model>`: Specific model variant to use via the huggingface API (e.g., meta-llama/Llama-2-13b-chat-hf, meta-llama/Meta-Llama-3-8B-

Instruct).

- <report_filename>: Path to the input .xlsx file containing pathology reports. (See PRAD_reports_eng.xlsx / PRAD_reports_ger.xlsx)
- <output_dir>: Directory where JSON output files will be saved.
- <stderr_out>: Directory where stderr output will be saved.

Running `inference\_4bit\_models.py`

- <report_filename>: Path to the input .xlsx file containing pathology reports. (See PRAD_reports_eng.xlsx / PRAD_reports_ger.xlsx)
- <output_dir>: Directory where JSON output files will be saved.
- <stderr_out>: Directory where stderr output will be saved.
- <model>: Select a model you have downloaded. Available model versions can be found on the Ollama homepage.
 - **Note:** Ensure Ollama is properly installed and configured with access to the specified models.

Running `inference\_4bit\_cov.py`

- <report_filename>: Path to the input .xlsx file containing pathology reports. (See PRAD_reports_eng.xlsx / PRAD_reports_ger.xlsx)
- <input_dir>: Path to a directory containing the Zero-shot JSON files.
- <output_dir>: Directory where JSON output files will be saved.
- <stderr_out>: Directory where stderr output will be saved.
- <model>: Select a model you have downloaded. Available model versions can be found on the Ollama homepage.
 - **Note:** Ensure Ollama is properly installed and configured with access to the specified models.

Running `json\_processing.py`

- <json_directory>: Directory containing JSON files from inference scripts.
- <path_to_annotations>: Path to the ground truth annotations .xlsx file. (See PRAD_ground_truth.xlsx)
- <output_directory>: Directory where processed results will be saved.

R Scripts

Running `analysis\_16bit.R` + `Running analysis\_4bit.R`

- Ensure that the processed results from json_processing.py etc. are available and correctly referenced in the scripts.
- Modify any paths or parameters within the scripts as needed for your specific environment or data structure.
- Depending on folder structure and file names some adaptations of the scripts are needed.

Output Files

From `inference_GPT4.py`, `inference_llama2.py`, `inference_llama3.py`, `inference_4bit_models.py` and `inference_4bit_cov.py`

- **JSON Files:** Structured data for each pathology report saved in the specified output directory.
- **Error Logs:** Logs detailing issues encountered during JSON exporting.

From `json_processing.py`

- **Results Table (`*_results.csv`):** Consolidated data comparing extracted information with ground truth annotations.
- **Key Frequency per Report (`*_var_stats.tsv`):** Summary occurrences of JSON keys per files (checks if a key occurs more than once in a JSON).
- **JSON Status Report (`json_status.tsv`):** Details on the structural integrity and preprocessing needs of each JSON file.

From R Scripts

- **Statistical Analysis Reports:**
 - Detailed performance metrics and comparisons
- **Figures and Plots:**
 - High-quality visualizations (e.g., PNG, PDF formats) illustrating model performances, error analyses, and other relevant statistics
- **Supplementary Materials:**
 - Additional tables and charts

Acknowledgements

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